

NEEDLE-PUNCHED NON-WOVEN FOR HIGH FRAGMENT PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

Physical properties of needle-punched non-woven made with high performance ballistic fibers, such as ultra high strength Polyethylene fibers, aramid and PBO fibers, may be designed to provide very high fragment resistance at a much lower weight than conventional fabrics.

The performance of such needle-punched non-woven may be engineered by changing fiber type, fiber size, staple length, punch density, blending of fibers, areal density and thickness.

This paper focuses on the characteristics and ballistic performance of non-woven manufactured on commercial needle-punch equipment producing various areal densities. Testing was conducted in accordance with the procedure of MIL-STD-662F, using Caliber .22, Type 2, 17-grain fragment simulators conforming to MIL-P-46593A.

The test data is presented for non-woven for a number of areal densities and also compared with high performance woven fabrics made with high performance ballistic fibers.

Data for a few selected commercial applications are also presented against high velocity fragments resistance at the lowest areal weight.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern warfare includes a number of modes of attack that make many concepts of mobile infantry, air cavalry and the highly specialized fighting vehicle of the past obsolete or at least obsolescent. In the present state, the available armor and critical component protection devices are too heavy and difficult to manipulate for optimum effectiveness. In the battlefield environment itself, protective structures that are light, mobile and easy to deploy can provide protection for troops, logistical support, medical teams and civilians caught in battle or terrorist attack situations. Lighter, yet more protective, shrapnel and fragment protection covers are needed immediately to counter existing and future threats.

Research at Auburn University and Honeywell Performance Fibers has led to the development of a special blended non-woven fabric of various fiber compositions and arrangements that enhances or replaces the function of conventional woven and shield fabrics. Test results at the university and at various independent testing facilities indicate that the resulting material acts to deflect, destabilize and stop the trajectories of steel fragment simulating projectiles.

The material technology in the area of flexible and rigid armor has improved substantially in the last decade. Due to these new technologies, military and law enforcement agencies around the world have added protection, comfort and substantially reduced the weight of the vests. The

technological changes are a result of a number of factors, including the new lightweight high strength ballistic fibers and the new development in the area of traditional weaving and technology breakthrough in the area of non-woven unidirectional ballistic composites.

This paper covers the recent advances in the area of ballistic for flexible body armor system and the ballistic fibers and technologies associated with engaging maximum number of fibers either in area of non-woven materials to the penetrating projectiles.

2. BALLISTIC MATERIALS

All categories of ballistic resistant materials have certain common characteristics. The use of polymer materials has made the performance-to-weight ratio a very favorable consideration for their use over metals or ceramics. Lower weight permits greater mobility and better capability for military aviation platforms to perform their assignments with reduced threats from attackers.

The commercial ballistic materials consist of man-made high performance ballistic fibers. Two common ballistic fibers are aromatic amide (aramids, commercially known by their trade name as Kevlar[®] or Twaron[®]) and Extended Chain Polyethylene (commercially known as Spectra[®] or Dyneema[®]). These fibers are further processed to generate either a woven fabric roll or a non-woven unidirectional roll.

A new family of ballistic fibers has commercialized recently. The fibers are relatively new, commonly known as PBO (poly-benzobisoxazole). The ballistic performance of this fiber shows substantial improvement for flexible vests. Military and other testing continues on this fiber as certain characteristics indicate a need for improvements in some categories before widespread use can be made of it.

2.1 ARAMID FIBERS

The aramid fibers are the second-generation ballistic fibers to provide higher ballistic protection compared to the ballistic nylon fibers utilized in the early 1960's.

Since the late 1980's, a number of new aramid fibers were introduced into the ballistic market. The basic chemistry of these new and improved fibers is the same as the original fibers introduced in the 1960's; but, these fibers have higher physical properties. The second improvement for aramid fibers is a lower denier and thinner fibers. The lower denier and improved physical properties of the fibers play an important role in defining the ballistic characteristics of a woven or non-woven unidirectional material.

2.2 EXTENDED CHAIN POLYETHYLENE

The Extended Chain Polyethylene fibers (ECPE), commercially called Spectra[®] fibers, were introduced in mid 1980's. A unique gel spinning process manufactures these fibers. Due to the chemistry of these highly oriented fibers, the fibers are practically inert to a host of chemicals and moisture. The new generation of fiber, introduced in the early 1990's, has higher physical properties. The second improvement is the lower denier and thinner fibers. The ballistic property of a woven and a non-woven fabric depends on the denier of the fibers and the physical properties of the fibers.

Ballistic resistant materials for military purposes fall into three categories: 1) garments and worn items such as vests and helmets; 2) vehicle reinforcement and 3) building and other structural reinforcements. The vests, jackets and similar garments are often mainly for protection against shrapnel and bomb fragments.

3. THREAT LEVEL DEFINITION

The U.S. Standard for ballistic threats that is used by suppliers of fabrics and fibers to compare performance of products is from the National Institute of Justice (NIJ). It identifies four levels of threat plus two subparts (Table 1). These levels range from rather low velocity or low mass projectiles at Level I to very high velocity, high mass projectiles at Level IV. It is sometimes useful in armor studies to look at the energy of a projectile impacting a target in terms of the area of the projectile. By this method, one can see, for example, why a .22 caliber bullet can be more dangerous to body armor than a .45 ACP round. Additionally, this method shows clearly the penetration power of rifle and machine gun rounds. Despite the penetration capabilities of 7.62mm rounds, the larger diameter .50 caliber BMG is still overwhelmingly superior to smaller ammunition. A graphical representation of the armor penetrating energy in joules of a wide range of projectiles is shown in Figure 1.

4. FABRIC STRUCTURE

Understanding the way a structure absorbs and dissipates energy allows engineering of a fabric for ballistic resistance. Strain wave velocity is the speed at which a fiber or structure can absorb and disperse strain energy, expressed as $v = \sqrt{F/\mu}$, wherein v = strain wave velocity; F = force (from projectile); and μ = linear density expressed as kg/m.

At the same time, one can also express v as $\sqrt{E/\rho}$, where E = Young's modulus and ρ = specific gravity of material.

The dissipation of impact energy by a structure is a measure of how efficient the energy absorption mechanism is (1,5). The fiber response to a projectile strike is elongation, slippage and breakage. Structures that optimize each of these properties yield the best ballistic performance (6,7,8).

Woven fabric dissipates energy at yarn interlacings. Energy is distributed along the yarn axis to each interlacing point. About one third of a fabric's strength loss occurs as a result of weaving. The remaining strength loss results from mechanical interaction between warp and weft yarns during tensile loading. High warp crimp in a woven structure is accompanied by low strength translation efficiency (2).

5. NON-WOVEN FABRICS

Conventional fabric processes require many steps, and manufacturing is relatively costly (1,10). Honeywell Performance Fibers divides the non-woven types of ballistic resistant fabrics into two categories. One is comprised of continuous filaments and the other is composed entirely of staple fibers. Some of the shortcomings of the woven fabrics are eliminated in the non-woven fabrics. The main advantages are the elimination of twisting, kinks, and fiber to fiber rubbing. All these factors improve the ballistic performance of these materials.

5.1 CROSSPLIED NON-WOVENS

In this process all the fibers are lined parallel to each other, similar to the beam operation in woven fabric, and then a binder is applied to form into a continuous web of aligned fibers. The web holds the fibers spacing for further processing. A web of similar aligned fibers is applied at 90 degrees to form a continuous roll. The 0 degree and 90 degree webs are further consolidated to form a unidirectional crossplied roll product.

The roll product developed by this technology is a patented process; commercially this material is called shield. The shield technology is applicable to all types of continuous ballistic fibers such as ECPE fibers, aramid and PBO fibers. GOLD FLEX[®] is a second-generation shield, based on aramid fibers. GOLD FLEX[®] offers a number of advantages over woven aramid fabric made with the identical fibers. This includes thinner, substantially higher performance for a number of steel-jacketed bullets and additional flexibility to the vest. Due to the nature of GOLD FLEX[®], practically no stitching is required to hold the vest for multiple hits.

5.2 NEEDLE-PUNCHED NON-WOVEN (NEEDLE FELTS)

Needle-punching is a simpler operation than weaving by which a variety of properties can be obtained in the fabric by varying the process components (6,11,12,13). Continuous ballistic fibers are chopped into smaller fibers, carded and (usually) randomly oriented by crosslapping to form an isotropic mat or sheet. This sheet is subsequently consolidated by a set of barbed needles. The needles push a limited amount of fibers at 90-degree through the sheet of randomly oriented fiber felt. The felt material engages fragments much better than traditional woven fabrics.

A 1966 U.S. Department of Defense study found that a needle-punched structure containing ballistic resistant nylon could be produced at one third the weight of a woven duck fabric while retaining 80% of its ballistic resistance (6). The process is still being used with success today in special applications.

Tests conducted by Auburn University indicate that combinations of aramid and ECPE fibers in non-woven blends give exceptional performance by combining the advantages of both fiber types. The new fabric type is called "ArmorFelt." Energy absorption properties 30% greater than in unblended structures were observed (Figure 2). The combination of thermoplastic and non-thermoplastic fibers in the structure allowed an energy dissipation mechanism by phase change that boosted the fabric areal weight performance (14). A lighter version of the product called "TraumaShield" protects a body from high energy impact after a bullet is stopped.

5.3 BLENDED NON-WOVEN

In original tests to develop a blended non-woven ballistic fabric, samples were produced by ITT, Charlottesville, Virginia, using carded and crosslapped webs. Three conditions of fibers were processed: 100% aramid, 3 inch fiber; 100% aramid, 4 inch fiber; a blend of 50% aramid, 3 inch fiber by weight and 50% Spectra[®] fibers 1000, 3 inch fiber by weight. The web was layered nine times to give a desired predrafted weight. Webs were processed through a preneedler for stability and then given a final needling to achieve punch densities of 400, 700, 1000 penetrations per square inch.

6. BALLISTIC TESTING

The projectile used in ballistic testing was a Type 1, .22 caliber, 17 grain fragment-simulating projectile as described in the publication MIL-P-46593A (MU), "Military Specification: Projectile, Calibers .22, .30, .50, and 20 MM Fragment-Simulating". Ballistic resistance was determined from three complete penetrations and three partial penetrations of samples at projectile velocities confined in the range of ± 6 m/sec. The target had an aluminum witness plate six inches behind it. If the projectile penetrated the witness plate, it completely penetrated the sample as well.

As density of the aramid fiber fabrics increased so did ballistic resistance. As more mass was compressed into a smaller volume, the ballistic resistance of the fabric was increased. Punch densities in the range of 700 to 1000 were shown to give the highest V50 value for both aramid fiber types. The four inch fiber condition results give good indication of the extent to which punch density affects V50 value. These

results indicate that 1000 ppsi and 700 ppsi produced significantly higher V50 values than 400 ppsi, but they were not significantly different from one another.

6.1 ECPE -- ARAMID BLEND

The 50/50 Spectra® fibers/aramid fabric thickness was significantly less than the 3 inch and 4 inch aramid fiber conditions. Fiber denier differences between the aramid and Spectra® fibers fibers contributed substantially to the effect. The Spectra® fibers fibers were 5.5 dpf; the aramid fibers were 1.5 dpf. As a result of their higher denier, Spectra® fibers fibers present in the blend afforded more voids in the blended needle-punched samples compared to the 100% aramid samples.

Since the final step in fabrication was to press the fabric at 3000 psi, this additional space in the blended samples compacted more easily and recovered less than the 100% aramid samples. Taking the specific gravity and denier differences between the aramid and Spectra® fibers into consideration, there was 37% less fiber present in the blended samples than in the 100% aramid samples. The blended samples contain 27% Spectra® fibers fibers, and 73% aramid fibers by numerical populations.

ANOVA indicated that punch density had a significant effect on thickness. By increasing punch density, the thickness of the fabric decreased. As the fabric was continually needled to higher punch densities, it condensed into a more compact structure. Overall, fiber type was a significant source of variation in fabric density. The density of the Spectra® fibers/aramid blend fabric was significantly greater than the 100% aramid conditions.

The Spectra® fibers/aramid blend had the best ballistic resistance followed by the aramid 3 inch fiber and aramid 4inch fiber conditions. The Spectra® fibers fiber denier and specific gravity should be considered when evaluating the differences between the blended and aramid conditions. For the blended fabric, optimum V50 values were shown to increase as the punch density approached 400 ppsi. Punch densities of 400 ppsi and 700 ppsi gave significantly higher ballistic resistance than 1000 ppsi, but were not significantly different from one another.

Ballistic resistance was enhanced with increases from 4 layers to 8 layers. Web layers had less effect in the Spectra® fibers /aramid blends than in the 100% aramid samples. As the number of layers was increased, the differences between the blended conditions and the 100% aramid became less, but they retained significance. Variation in density showed a similar response of V50 ballistic resistance with varying fabric density for the different fiber type conditions.

Further testing of the fragmentation stopping capability of blended non-woven fabrics continued between 1997 and 2001. Among findings during this development, it was clear that significant advantage exists where ECPE fibers are 5.5 denier or finer. Disadvantage was observed when fiber blends with PBO present were tested because of the very low frictional characteristics of these fibers.

6.2 FRAGMENT PROTECTION

Non-woven, needle-punched, ballistic resistant fabrics developed at Auburn University were tested in 2002 at both Honeywell Performance Fibers Laboratory in Petersburg, Virginia and the U.S. Army Aberdeen Proving Grounds, against woven aramid fabrics and against woven PBO fabric to compare performances in defeating explosion fragments. In the military spec tests, flexible armor was tested against the most common specified fragment threat (MIL-STR-662F). Results of fragment testing at Honeywell are shown in Table 2.

6.2.1 TESTS BY U.S. ARMY

Evaluation of the blended non-woven was conducted as a part of the development of a fragment resistant cover for the Army's LOSAT KEM trailer. In the test, at Aberdeen Proving Grounds, the parameters were weight of 0.75 pounds/square foot or less and projectile speed of 1400 feet/second (425 meters/sec) or more. The test results determined conclusively that Auburn's ArmorFelt outperformed woven aramid and woven PBO by a large difference. (Figure 5)

7. SOFT BODY ARMOR

A significant factor which has contributed to soft armor advances is the hybrid concept of combining more than one ballistic material in a single armor system. This technique allows armor design engineers to utilize full potential of various ballistic materials.

Combinations of conventional materials and/or shield based products with ArmorFelt have shown significant advantages when used against rated soft body armor threats. Testing of these systems using NIJ 0101.04 Level IIIA Standard, .44 Magnum is shown in Tables 3 through 5.

8. PROTECTION FROM EXPLOSION

Tests conducted by Auburn University Textile Engineering in 2003 have shown that adding ArmorFelt to woven aramid fabrics creates a structure that can withstand explosion blasts better than woven aramids by themselves. In tests using nitroglycerin based dynamite in steel containment chambers to intensify blast effects, nine layers of woven aramids were not able to withstand the blast energy of 1/2 stick of nitroglycerin based dynamite. An equal weight structure of 2 layers of aramid, 5 layers ArmorFelt and 2 more layers of aramid successfully suppressed the explosion with no problem.

9. SUMMARY

The technologies developed by Auburn University, USA using technologies of Honeywell Performance Fibers can be utilized to provide a large range of protection for military and civilian applications.

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Table 1. National Institute of Justice Standards for Ballistic Resistance

Threat Level	Caliber	Projectile Description	Weight (Grains)	Velocity (Ft/Sec)
I	.22 Long Rifle	Lead	40	1080
I	.380 ACP	Full Metal Jacket	95	1055
II-A	9 mm	Full Metal Jacket	124	1120
II-A	.40 S&W	Full Metal Jacket	180	1055
II	9 mm	Full Metal Jacket	124	1205
II	.357 Magnum	Jacketed Soft Point	158	1430
III-A	9 mm	Full Metal Jacket	124	1430
III-A	.44 Magnum	Jacketed Soft Point	240	1430
III	7.62 mm NATO	Full Metal Jacket	148	2780
IV	.30-06	Armor Piercing	166	2880

Table 2. Comparative Averages of Fragment (FSP) Testing on Flexible Armor System

Material	Number of Plies	Areal Density (psf)	V50 (ft/sec)
GF	25	1.19	1924
AF+ GF	2+23	1.19	1887
GF + AF	23+2	1.19	1944
AF	15	0.74	1880

Legend: GF = GOLD FLEX[®]; AF = ArmorFelt

Table 3. Level IIIA Baseline Test Results GOLD FLEX[®] Only

Sample	Material	Bullet type	Speed	Penetration	Backface Deformation
1	24 GOLD FLEX [®]	.44 mag JHP	1422	p	47
2	1.14 psf	.44 mag JHP	1438	p	42
3		.44 mag JHP	1450	p	41
4		.44 mag JHP	1438	p	42
5		.44 mag JHP	1449	p	47
6		.44 mag JHP	1427	p	49
Averages			1437.33 3		44.66667

Table 4. Level IIIA Test Results GOLD FLEX + 4 Ply ArmorFelt

Sample	Material	Bullet Type	Speed	Penetration	Backface Deformation
1	19 GOLD FLEX®	.44 mag JHP	1442	p	39
2	1 felt 4 ply	.44 mag JHP	1446	p	38
3	1.14 psf	.44 mag JHP	1443	p	37
4		.44 mag JHP	1448	p	43
5		.44 mag JHP	1452	p	35
6		.44 mag JHP	1461	p	42
Averages			1440.317		38.78333

Table 5. Level IIIA Test Results GOLD FLEX® + 3 Ply ArmorFelt

Sample	Material	Bullet Type	Speed	Penetration	Backface Deformation
1	18 GOLD FLEX®	.44 mag JHP	1402	p	40
2	1 felt 3 ply	.44 mag JHP	1411	p	39
3	1.11 psf	.44 mag JHP	1410	p	39
4		.44 mag JHP	1435	p	40
5		.44 mag JHP	1444	p	38
6		.44 mag JHP	1413	p	37
Averages			1419.167		38.83333

Figure 1

Figure 1. Foot pounds energy/square inch delivered to a target by various ammunitions

Energy absorption in ECPE, aramid blends

- ◆ Radiated strain energy
 - transferred by aramids and ECPE outside impact
- ◆ Fibrillation of aramids
- ◆ Phase change induced in ECPE

Figure 2. Results of aramid and ECPE fabric ballistic impact

Fragment armor improvements with ArmorFelt technology

- ◆ Results* from US Army Aberdeen Proving Grounds test
 - ◆ .22 cal. 17 grain, fragment simulating projectile, steel
- ◆ Parameters :
 - ◆ Weight < 0.7 lbs/ft²
 - ◆ Projectile speed > 425 m/sec (1400fps)
- ◆ Nonwoven materials were superior to woven aramid and woven PBO
- ◆ Historical development of nonwoven armor-
 - ◆ Original Kevlar 29 = 1275 fps
 - ◆ Original (1991) blend gave 1425 fps (ECPE, 2nd quality and Kevlar 29)

* Test results 31 August – 1 September 2002

Figure 3 Performance of ArmorFelt in Fragment Defeat